

PHASE VOCODERS WITH ARBITRARY FREQUENCY BAND SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

Time-frequency representations play a central role in sound analysis and synthesis. While most of the conventional methods are based on phase vocoders with uniform frequency bands, perception and physical characteristics of sound signals suggest the need for nonuniform bands.

In this paper we propose a flexible design of a phase vocoder having arbitrary frequency band divisions. The design is based on recently developed nonuniform frames where here frequency warping, i.e. a remapping of the frequency axis, is employed for the design of the sliding windows, which are different for each frequency channel.

We show that tight frames can be obtained with this method, which allow for perfect reconstruction with identical analysis and synthesis time-frequency atoms. The transform and its inverse have computationally efficient implementations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Time-frequency representations play a central role in the analysis, synthesis, coding and processing of sound signals. In this context, the most commonly used representation is the phase vocoder [1] or Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), which has uniform time and frequency resolutions. However, non-uniform resolution is desirable in several applications. For example, the analysis and synthesis frequency bands can be adapted to a perceptual scale, achieving clear advantages in synthesis and coding due to the direct psycho-acoustic relevance of each component. In synthesis-by-analysis schemes, the frequency bands can be adapted to characteristics of the signal suggested, for example, by the frequencies of the partials of the tones, which in many instruments, such as the piano in the low register or percussions, are not harmonically related.

Non-uniform frequency bands can always be thought of as obtained from uniform bands through a frequency map, i.e. a monotonically increasing function remapping the frequency axis, as shown in Fig. 1. In certain cases, e.g. critical bands, the frequency map is given by experimentally

Figure 1. Example of frequency warping map, mapping uniform bands (ordinate) into nonuniform bands (abscissa).

fitted curves. In other cases, such as in the vibration of stiff strings or bars, the frequency map is derived from a wave dispersion characteristic. Sometimes the map is only specified at a finite number of points; a continuous curve can be obtained by interpolation. The application of a frequency map is known in filter design as frequency warping.

In this paper, based on recently developed results [2, 3], we address the problem of building perfect reconstruction structures for the time-frequency representation of signals that allow for arbitrary selection of bands specified according to a frequency map. Mathematically this amounts to constructing flexible frames that allow for parametric selection of the frequency bands of their atoms.

The paper is organized as follows. In this section we continue by illustrating the basics of Gabor and warped Gabor frames. In Section 2 we introduce the new concept of nonuniform Gabor frames and their dual frames designed by means of frequency warping. In Section 3 we illustrate some applications of the methods and in Section 4 we draw our conclusions.

1.1 Gabor frames

A sequence $(\psi_l)_{l \in I}$ in the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is called a *frame*, if there exist positive constants A and B (called lower and upper frame bounds, respectively) such that

$$A\|f\|^2 \leq \sum_{l \in I} |\langle f, \psi_l \rangle|^2 \leq B\|f\|^2 \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{H}, \quad (1)$$

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i.e. $\sum_{l \in I} |\langle f, \psi_l \rangle|^2 \simeq \|f\|^2$. If $A = B$, then $(\psi_l)_{l \in I}$ is a *tight frame*. By $\mathbf{C} : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \ell^2$, we denote the *analysis operator* defined by $(\mathbf{C}f)_l = \langle f, \psi_l \rangle$. The adjoint of \mathbf{C}^* of \mathbf{C} is the *synthesis operator* $\mathbf{C}^*(c_l) = \sum_l c_l \psi_l$. The *frame operator* is $\mathbf{S}f = \mathbf{C}^*\mathbf{C}f = \sum_l \langle f, \psi_l \rangle \psi_l$, hence $\langle \mathbf{S}f, f \rangle = \|\mathbf{C}f\|_{\ell^2}^2$.

The boundedness and invertibility of \mathbf{S} is equivalent to the existence of frame bounds $0 < A, B < \infty$ in the frame inequality (1), as well as to the existence of *dual frames*, which can be used for reconstruction. In particular, the *canonical dual frame* $(\tilde{\psi}_l)$, is found by applying the inverse of \mathbf{S} to the original frame elements, i.e. $\tilde{\psi}_l = \mathbf{S}^{-1}\psi_l$ for all l . For all $f \in \mathcal{H}$ we then have the following reconstruction formulas:

$$f = \sum_l \langle f, \psi_l \rangle \tilde{\psi}_l = \sum_l \langle f, \tilde{\psi}_l \rangle \psi_l.$$

For tight frames, the frame operator reduces to $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{I}$, where \mathbf{I} denotes the identity operator, and therefore $\mathbf{S}^{-1} = \frac{1}{A}\mathbf{I}$. The *canonical tight frame* $(\hat{\psi}_l)$ is obtained by applying $\mathbf{S}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ to the frame elements, i.e. $\hat{\psi}_l = \mathbf{S}^{-\frac{1}{2}}\psi_l$ for all l .

For any nonzero function $g \in L^2(\mathbb{R})$ (the *window*), the *short-time Fourier transform* (STFT) of a signal $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R})$ is defined as $\mathcal{V}_g(f)(\xi, \nu) = \langle f, \mathbf{M}_\nu \mathbf{T}_\xi g \rangle$, using the *translation operator* $\mathbf{T}_\xi f(t) = f(t - \xi)$ and the *modulation operator* $\mathbf{M}_\nu f(t) = f(t) e^{j2\pi\nu t}$. In $L^2(\mathbb{R})$, we have

$$\mathcal{V}_g(f)(\xi, \nu) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(t) \overline{g(t - \xi)} e^{-j2\pi\nu t} dt.$$

For a non-zero window function g and parameters $\tau, b > 0$, the set of time-frequency shifts of g

$$\mathcal{G}(g, \tau, b) = \{\mathbf{M}_{qb} \mathbf{T}_{n\tau} g : q, n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

is called a *Gabor system* [4]. Moreover, if $\mathcal{G}(g, \tau, b)$ is a frame, it is called a *Gabor frame*. Note that the Gabor analysis coefficients are sampling points of the STFT of f with window g at the time-frequency points $(n\tau, qb)$.

Since $\mathbf{M}_\nu \mathbf{T}_\xi = e^{j2\pi\nu\xi} \mathbf{T}_\xi \mathbf{M}_\nu$, then, up to irrelevant time independent phase factors, one can provide Gabor systems in the form

$$\mathcal{G}^\sharp(g, \tau, b) = \{\mathbf{T}_{n\tau} \mathbf{M}_{qb} g : q, n \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

A central property of Gabor frames is the fact that the dual frame of a Gabor frame is again a Gabor frame, generated by the *dual window* $\tilde{g} = \mathbf{S}^{-1}g$ and the same *lattice*, i.e. the set of time-frequency points $\{(n\tau, qb) | n, q \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Note that the property that the dual system is again a system with the same structure, is a particular property of Gabor frames, shared by nonstationary Gabor frames in the painless setting, described in Section 2.1.

1.2 Warping Gabor frames

Any unitary operation on the frame results in a new frame with the same frame bounds A and B [5]. In particular, unitary operators can be applied to Gabor frames to obtain new frames. Depending on the operator, the resulting

frames are not necessarily of the Gabor type, as the atoms are not generated by translating and modulating a single window function.

A frequency warping operator is completely characterized by a function composition operator in the frequency domain, transforming the Fourier transform \hat{s} of a signal s into the Fourier transform \hat{s}_w of another signal s_w :

$$\hat{s}_w = \hat{s} \circ \theta \quad (2)$$

where θ is the warping map. If the map is one-to-one and almost everywhere differentiable then a unitary form of the warping operator can be defined by the action

$$\hat{s}(\nu) = \left[\widehat{\mathbf{U}_\theta s} \right](\nu) = \sqrt{\left| \frac{d\theta}{d\nu} \right|} \hat{s}(\theta(\nu)). \quad (3)$$

In particular, when applied to a Gabor frame, the unitary warping operator \mathbf{U}_θ generates the frequency warped frame $\{\varphi_{n,q}\}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$ and dual frame $\{\gamma_{n,q}\}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{n,q} &= \mathbf{U}_\theta \mathbf{T}_{n\tau} \mathbf{M}_{qb} g, \\ \gamma_{n,q} &= \mathbf{U}_\theta \mathbf{T}_{n\tau} \mathbf{M}_{qb} \tilde{g} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The computation of signal expansions over warped frames requires the generation of sets of warped delayed and modulated windows. Since by warping the time shift operator is transformed into a frequency dependent shift, the windows are not simply translated and, in principle, they have infinite support in the time domain.

Alternately, in the computation one can inversely warp the signal and project it onto a regular Gabor frame. Besides issues linked to the complexity and noncausality of the warping operation, the in-band frequency dependent delays tend to hide or destroy the time structure of the signals, which is a negative factor in signal visualization and synthesis.

In the next section we introduce approximations of the frequency warped frames that allow for a more intuitive time organization, while preserving perfect reconstruction properties.

2. APPROXIMATELY WARPED FRAMES

In this section we explore new frames that are inspired by the warped frames but have better or more intuitive properties for sound and music computing.

One of the main problems with warped frames is the presence of frequency dependent delays resulting from frequency warping the time shift operator. The frequency dependency of the delay shows up even within the analysis or synthesis bands. However, conceptually, if the bandwidth of the original window is narrow, the frequency dependent time shift can be approximated by a constant incremental delay within the band.

Modulating the original window results in nonuniform frequency resolution controlled by the warping map. In each of these bands the incremental delay is constant but it varies band by band if the warping map is nonlinear. One could also interpret the variability of the time shift across the bands in terms of sampling: larger bandwidths require larger sampling rates, hence smaller time shifts.

A frame frequency channel dependent time shift was introduced in [3] and employed in a computationally efficient approximation for warping signals. Properties and applications of generalized Gabor frames having nonuniform frequency resolution were studied in [2].

2.1 Building generalized Gabor frames with arbitrary frequency bands

As described in Section 1.1, Gabor frames are obtained by uniformly time shifting and modulating a unique time window φ . Here we consider a generalization of Gabor frames that admits a different window φ_q and different time shift τ_q for each frequency channel indexed by q . In other words, the time-frequency atoms of the representation are the functions

$$\varphi_{n,q}(t) = \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\varphi_q(t) \quad n, q \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (5)$$

where the modulation is implicit in the windows, i.e., as q varies, the Fourier transforms of the windows $\hat{\varphi}_q$ occupy different frequency bands. Moreover, the bandwidths are allowed to be different and the center frequencies of the bands are not necessarily harmonically related.

The frequency bands of the functions $\hat{\varphi}_q$ are allowed to overlap. Intuitively, a necessary condition for the invertibility of the representation is that there are no gaps or zeros in the total superposition of frequency bands. As we will see, together with the boundedness of the superposition, this is precisely the condition for the set of functions in (5) to form a frame.

The frame operator

$$\mathbf{S}f = \sum_{n,q} \langle f, \varphi_{n,q} \rangle \varphi_{n,q} \quad (6)$$

associated with (5), where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes scalar product in $L^2(\mathbb{R})$, has Fourier representation

$$\widehat{\mathbf{S}}f(\nu) = \sum_q \frac{1}{\tau_q} \sum_m \hat{f}\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right) \overline{\hat{\varphi}_q\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right)} \hat{\varphi}_q(\nu) \quad (7)$$

in which the Fourier transform of the signal $\hat{f}(\nu)$ appears together with its frequency aliased versions $\hat{f}\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right)$ for $m \neq 0$.

If the frame operator is invertible one can show that upper and lower frame bounds can be determined and that a dual frame $\{\gamma_{n,q}\}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$ can be provided as follows

$$\gamma_{n,q} = \mathbf{S}^{-1}\varphi_{n,q} \quad (8)$$

In fact, in these circumstances, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f &= \mathbf{S}^{-1}\mathbf{S}f = \sum_{n,q} \langle f, \varphi_{n,q} \rangle \mathbf{S}^{-1}\varphi_{n,q} \\ &= \sum_{n,q} \langle f, \varphi_{n,q} \rangle \gamma_{n,q} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Since the time-shift operators $\mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}$ do not necessarily commute with the frame operator inverse, in general the

dual frame is not obtained by shifting windows functions, i.e.,

$$\gamma_{n,q}(t) = \mathbf{S}^{-1}\mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\varphi_q(t) \neq \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\mathbf{S}^{-1}\varphi_q(t) = \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\gamma_q(t) \quad (10)$$

In cases where the commutation rule

$$\mathbf{S}^{-1}\mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q} = \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\mathbf{S}^{-1} \quad (11)$$

is satisfied, one can show that the following condition must be fulfilled:

$$\sum_{q,m} \frac{e^{j2\pi nm \frac{\tau_p}{\tau_q}}}{\tau_q} \hat{\gamma}_p\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right) \overline{\hat{\varphi}_q\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right)} \hat{\gamma}_q(\nu) = \hat{\gamma}_p(\nu) \quad (12)$$

almost everywhere in $\nu \in \mathbb{R}$ and for any $n, p \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Known cases where (12) can be satisfied are uniform Gabor frames and wavelet tight frames and bases. In the frequency domain, inversion of the frame operator requires means to cancel the frequency aliased versions of \hat{f} , which may be complex to achieve in the general case.

In the so called ‘‘painless’’ case [6], the windows are chosen to have compact support in the frequency domain, and the time shifts τ_q are chosen so that in (7) the product

$$\overline{\hat{\varphi}_q\left(\nu - \frac{m}{\tau_q}\right)} \hat{\varphi}_q(\nu) = 0 \quad \text{for } m \neq 0 \quad (13)$$

That is, the aliased versions of each window have no overlap with the window itself. This is simply achieved by selecting

$$\tau_q \leq \frac{1}{B_q} \quad (14)$$

where B_q is the bandwidth or length of the support of $\hat{\varphi}_q(\nu)$, where we assume that the support is an interval.

As shown in the next section, this assumption provides great simplifications for the definition of frames with arbitrary band allocation since the frame operator has diagonal Fourier representation (7).

2.2 Dual frames

While in general the inversion of the operator \mathbf{S} poses a problem in numerical realization, we know that under certain conditions, often fulfilled in practical applications, \mathbf{S} is diagonal, in time or frequency domain, as described above. We use windows with adaptive, compact bandwidth and choose the time-shift parameters dependent on the bandwidth of each window: the time-sampling points have to be chosen dense enough to guarantee (14).

Under these conditions on the windows φ_q and the hop-sizes τ_q , the frame operator is diagonal in the Fourier domain: since, by unitarity of the Fourier transform and the Walnut representation of the frame operator [7], we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{S}f, f \rangle &= \sum_{n,q} |\langle f, \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q}\varphi_q \rangle|^2 = \sum_{n,q} |\langle \hat{f}, \mathbf{M}_{-n\tau_q}\hat{\varphi}_q \rangle|^2 \\ &= \langle \hat{\lambda}\hat{f}, \hat{f} \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

with

$$\hat{\lambda} = \sum_q \frac{1}{\tau_q} |\hat{\varphi}_q|^2 \quad (15)$$

the frame operator assumes the following form:

$$\mathbf{S}f = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\hat{\lambda}\hat{f}) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\hat{\lambda}) * f. \quad (16)$$

See [6, 8, 9] for detailed proofs of the diagonality of the frame operator in the described setting. From (14), it follows immediately that the frame operator is invertible whenever there exist real numbers numbers A and B such that the inequalities

$$0 < A \leq \sum_q \frac{1}{\tau_q} |\hat{\varphi}_q|^2 \leq B < \infty \quad (17)$$

hold almost everywhere. In this case, the dual frame is given by the elements

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{n,q} &:= \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left[\mathbf{M}_{-n\tau_q} \left(\hat{\varphi}_q / \hat{\lambda} \right) \right] \\ &= \mathbf{T}_{n\tau_q} \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left[\left(\hat{\varphi}_q / \hat{\lambda} \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Based on the implementation of nonstationary Gabor frames performing adaptivity in the time domain, the above framework permits a fast realization of frequency-adaptive Gabor frames by considering the Fourier transform of the input signal. The transform coefficients $c_{n,q} = \langle f, \varphi_{n,q} \rangle$ take the form

$$c_{n,q} = \langle \hat{f}, \mathbf{M}_{-n\tau_q} \hat{\varphi}_q \rangle, \quad (18)$$

and can be calculated, for each q , from the FFT of the signal with a number of operations solely determined by the support of $\hat{\varphi}_q$. Similarly, reconstruction is realized by applying the windows $\mathbf{M}_{-n\tau_q} \hat{\gamma}_q$, where $\hat{\gamma}_q = \hat{\varphi}_q / \hat{\lambda}$, in a simple overlap-add process. Whenever perfect reconstruction is necessary, the transform parameters must be chosen, such that conditions (14) and (17) are satisfied.

2.3 Designing frames with arbitrary band allocations by means of frequency warping

In [2] the design of "painless" frames with compact support in the frequency domain and arbitrary band allocation was approached by scaling the Von Hann window in the frequency domain.

In this section a new design is proposed, which is based on frequency warping. The main advantage of the new approach is that the bands can be allocated following a curve, the warping map, that can be derived from physical or perceptual characteristics of the signal. Another advantage is that by frequency warping one can obtain tight frames with arbitrary band allocation. While tight frames can also be obtained from the original design by reassigning the windows as follows

$$\hat{\varphi}_q \leftarrow \frac{\hat{\varphi}_q}{\sqrt{\sum_k \frac{1}{\tau_k} |\hat{\varphi}_k|^2}},$$

the denominator introduces in-band ripple due to the imperfect overlap of the original windows at transition bands.

The design based on warping eliminates the need for re-normalization and allows for smooth transition bands. It can be performed starting from any tight uniform Gabor frame.

To approach the new design, consider a nonnegative symmetric window $\hat{h}(\nu)$ in the frequency domain satisfying the requirement

$$\sum_q \hat{h}^2(\nu - bq) = 1 \quad (19)$$

for a certain $b > 0$. Several well-known windows satisfy (19). For example one can select the square root of the Von Hann window, i.e. the cosine window

$$\hat{h}(\nu) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2}{K}} \cos \frac{\pi\nu}{B} & \text{if } -\frac{B}{2} \leq \nu < +\frac{B}{2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $B > 0$ is the total bandwidth of the window and $K > 1$ is an integer. The cosine window satisfies (19) for $b = B/K$.

The frequency support of each of the windows $\hat{h}_q(\nu) = \hat{h}(\nu - bq)$ is the interval $[bq - \frac{B}{2}, bq + \frac{B}{2}]$.

In order to construct windows with nonuniform bandwidth one can start by prescribing a monotonically increasing, one-to-one, map θ of the frequency axis, which we assume henceforth to be an almost everywhere differentiable odd function of frequency. In practical applications, the map can be inspired by physical or perceptual characteristics. Otherwise, if only the desired center band frequencies ν_q are prescribed, one can build a smooth continuous map by interpolation from the pairs (ν_q, bq) .

To each of the functions $h_q = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\hat{h}_q]$ we apply a nonunitary warping operator \mathbf{W}_θ built as the operator \mathbf{U}_θ in (3) without the square root derivative factor. As a result, the uniformly spaced windows \hat{h}_q are transformed to the nonuniformly spaced frequency domain windows

$$\hat{g}_q(\nu) = \widehat{\mathbf{W}_\theta h_q}(\nu) = \hat{h}_q(\theta(\nu)) = \hat{h}(\theta(\nu) - bq) \quad (21)$$

Since (19) holds for any ν then warping preserves the constant overlap-add property:

$$\sum_q \hat{g}_q^2(\nu) = \sum_q \hat{h}^2(\theta(\nu) - bq) = 1 \quad (22)$$

The frequency domain shapes of the original windows are smoothly altered by the warping map so that the nonuniformly stretched windows blend nicely into each other.

The center frequencies ν_q of the warped windows are the solutions of the equations $\theta(\nu) - bq = 0$ that is:

$$\nu_q = \theta^{-1}(bq) \quad (23)$$

since the map is invertible. Similarly, the band edge frequencies ν_q^\pm are solutions of the equations $\theta(\nu) - bq = \pm B/2$, i.e.,

$$\nu_q^\pm = \theta^{-1}(bq \pm \frac{B}{2}) \quad (24)$$

Comparing (22) with (15) and (17), we see that by letting

$$\hat{\varphi}_q = \sqrt{\tau_q} \hat{g}_q \quad (25)$$

with the warped windows one can achieve

$$\hat{\lambda}(\nu) = \sum_q \frac{1}{\tau_q} |\hat{\varphi}_q(\nu)|^2 = 1 \quad (26)$$

That is, tight frames with unit frame bounds $A = B = 1$ can be generated with the warped uniform windows, in which case the dual frame $\{\gamma_{n,q}\}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$ coincides with the frame $\{\varphi_{n,q}\}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$.

The atoms of the frame and dual frame can be generated by time-shifting the inverse Fourier transforms of the windows as in (5). Since the supports of the warped windows are the intervals

$$\left[\theta^{-1} \left(bq - \frac{B}{2} \right), \theta^{-1} \left(bq + \frac{B}{2} \right) \right] \quad (27)$$

in order to fulfill (14) one needs to select

$$\tau_q \leq \frac{1}{\theta^{-1} \left(bq + \frac{B}{2} \right) - \theta^{-1} \left(bq - \frac{B}{2} \right)} \quad (28)$$

We remark that, if the bandwidth ν of the original window h is small, then

$$\begin{aligned} \theta^{-1} \left(bq + \frac{B}{2} \right) - \theta^{-1} \left(bq - \frac{B}{2} \right) &\approx B \left. \frac{d\theta^{-1}}{d\nu} \right|_{\nu=bq} \\ &= B \left(\left. \frac{d\theta}{d\nu} \right|_{\nu=\theta^{-1}(bq)} \right)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Thus, for the largest values of allowed time-shifts we have

$$\tau_q \approx \frac{\theta'(\theta^{-1}(bq))}{B} = \frac{\theta'(\theta^{-1}(bq))}{Kb} \quad (30)$$

Hence, if the map is identical, $\theta(\nu) = \nu$, we have $\tau_q b \approx 1/K$ as in the uniform Gabor case with redundancy overlap factor K .

In the warped case, the time-shifts are proportional to the approximate frequency dependent time-stretching of the narrow band windows due to frequency warping, which are given by group delay θ' evaluated at the center bands. Moreover, the normalization factors in (25) can be interpreted as proportional to the square root of the derivative of the warping map θ evaluated at the center bands of the warped windows, which approximately restores the normalization factor of the unitary warping operator (3) to the nonunitarily warped windows.

3. APPLICATIONS AND EXAMPLES

The flexibility in time-frequency tiling achieved by the arbitrary band vocoder described in this paper paves the way to several applications in sound and music computing, coding and music information retrieval. The tightness of the frames guarantees that the total energy of the signal is equal to the sum of the squares of the analysis coefficients and that no multiplicative bias is introduced in the analysis that is then taken away by the synthesis.

Figure 2. Warping the frame frequency channels according to Bark scale (top): resulting frequency band characteristics (bottom).

3.1 Adaptation to Desired Frequency Scales

The allocations of the bands of the frequency channels is performed by means of a frequency map θ , mapping nonuniform bands into uniform ones. It is convenient to normalize the map so that the desired center frequencies are mapped to integers denoting the channel indices. The map can be derived from perceptual, physical or musical scales.

An example of adapted frequency band characteristics is shown in Fig.2, where the map is directly obtained from the perceptual Bark scale [10], resulting in 25 channels with bandwidths increasing with frequency in the frequency range 0 to 22 KHz. It is apparent how the bands are not simply obtained by constant scaling: the frequency characteristics are more stretched for the upper band portions than for the lower ones.

Another example is reported in Fig. 3 where the frequency tiling is adapted to a 1/3 of octave scale, resulting in 33 channels. The arbitrariness of the map allows one to build frames tuned to any scale and pitch resolution.

3.2 Frequency Channels

Given the integer N obtained by rounding the maximum value of the normalized warping map, the bandwidth parameter b in (19) is selected by dividing the maximum frequency of the total range by N .

The actual number of frequency channels depends on the overlap factor K . For $K = 2$, useful in most applications, the final number of channels is given by $N + 1$, which includes the 0 frequency channel and the highest frequency channel that has support overlapping with the frequency range of the signal. When needed, the frequency response of the 0 frequency channel is obtained by fixing a lower bandwidth and summing together all the frequency windows having center frequency below the lower bandwidth.

For real signals, negative frequency channels can be obtained by complex conjugation of the corresponding posi-

Figure 3. Warping the frame frequency channels according to a 1/3 of octave scale (top): resulting frequency band characteristics (bottom).

tive frequency channel and do not need to be computed.

3.3 Implementation

In our implementation we employed an algorithm directly derived from (18) in which the FFT of the signal is first computed and the scalar products are computed in the frequency domain over the frequency support of the windows $\hat{\varphi}_q$. This algorithm is shown in [2] to have complexity $O(L \log L)$ for both analysis and synthesis, where L is the length of the signal.

Implementation is therefore very simple and it parallels in the frequency domain what is usually performed in the time domain, in terms of windowing for the analysis and overlap-add for the synthesis. At different time instants the windows only differ by a phase factor, which is easily obtained by multiplication.

3.4 Nonuniform Spectrograms

In order to display time-frequency spectrograms with synchronous time scale for all bands, it is convenient to compute the transform coefficients with time oversampling, choosing the sampling intervals τ_q in (28) to be all equal to their minimum value τ . This is always possible for finite bandwidth signals. In this case, at each time step one needs to modulate the DFT of the signal, multiplying it by $e^{j2\pi\nu\tau}$. Incidentally, should we modulate, at this step, by the factor $e^{j2\pi b\theta(\nu)\tau}$ instead, we would obtain a frequency domain implementation of the expansion over the warped Gabor frames in (4).

Here the frequency ν takes the discrete values $k\nu_s/L$, where $k \in \{0, \dots, L/2 - 1\}$, obtained from the FFT calculation, in which ν_s is the sampling rate of the signal. The modulated DFT of the signal is stored and reused in the next time step calculation.

The spectrogram based on the 12-tone equally tempered scale of a singing musical phrase is shown in Fig. 4, resulting in 118 frequency channels at $\nu_s = 44.1$ KHz. For

Figure 4. Nonuniform 12-tone scale spectrogram of singing phrase.

Figure 5. Uniform frequency scale spectrogram of singing phrase.

comparison, the uniform frequency band spectrogram of the same signal based on the same number of channels is shown in Fig. 5, using the same distribution of frequency bins. It is apparent how, at same computational cost, the 12-tone spectrogram better captures the musical score by zooming into the part of the time-frequency domain, where most energy of the signal is concentrated.

For another comparison, the spectrogram based on the warped Gabor frames (4) is reported in Fig. 6. One can notice how the presence of the dispersive delays destroys the time structure of the score.

As another application example suitable for coding applications, the nonuniform spectrogram based on 1/4 Bark scale (4 channels per Bark) of a complex rock music excerpt is shown in Fig. 7. For comparison, the uniform spectrogram is plotted below in Fig. 8. It is apparent how the perceptually relevant information is distributed in time-frequency by using the nonuniform spectrogram.

Figure 6. Warped Gabor spectrogram of singing phrase.

Figure 8. Uniform spectrogram of rock music excerpt.

Figure 7. Bark scale spectrogram of rock music excerpt.

3.5 Sound Computing Applications

The flexibility of the signal representation illustrated in this paper inspires a number of creative uses. For example, in the analysis and synthesis of sounds with nonharmonic partials one can adapt the frequency bands to capture the frequency content of the main partials, together with that of other bands lying in-between the given partials. If the frequency channels corresponding to the partials are suppressed, one can study the noise or fluctuations of the signal.

For example, in piano tones in the low register, one can extract the hammer noise by re-synthesizing all the non-partial bands. Vice versa, in denoising or audio restoration applications, one may want to suppress the side bands of the partials, which contain disturbing unmasked noise.

In an analysis-synthesis scheme similar to the one illustrated in [11], within the proposed signal representation one can allocate narrow bands centered on the frequencies of the signal's partials and wider left and right sidebands of the partials. This is realized by means of a pitch dependent smoothed staircase warping map, with higher slope around the frequencies of the partials and lower slope at the sidebands. The sidebands represent fluctuations of the partials

that can be often modeled as modulated $1/f$ noise, while the partials are represented by low-rate pitch and amplitude information. Perceptually, the presence of the fluctuations is relevant, while the details of the fluctuations are less relevant, which allows for coarser modeling of the sidebands. The flexibility of the presented scheme allows for accurate tuning of the representation bands, which is far less rigid than the allocation in [11].

In other applications as sound effects, one can use uniform bands for the analysis coupled with nonuniform bands for the synthesis with same coefficients. Thus, the frequency content of the signal in the analysis bands is displaced to other frequency bands in the synthesis, resulting in band stretching and modulation. In this way one obtains an efficient algorithm for frequency warping, similar to the one presented in [3].

In conventional uses of the phase vocoder, such as time stretching, frequency shifting and harmonizer, one is often interested in tracking the partials, which requires estimation of the instantaneous frequencies. This is usually performed by time differencing the phase of the transform coefficients, as evaluated at adjacent time instants. For the estimation to be successful one needs to have sufficiently narrow-band analysis atoms so that interference of distinct signal partials is low. The proposed transform allows us to design the frequency resolution arbitrarily assigning, e.g., higher resolution around the expected frequencies of the partials, which for most signals are in the lower frequency portion of the spectrum.

Even in the constant Q case, one can set the resolution to arbitrary fractions of a tone, as sufficient for frequency tracking. Mixed mode is also possible, e.g., by assigning uniform resolution at low frequencies and constant Q at high frequencies. Compared to orthogonal wavelets, whose resolution in the simplest and most popular case is one octave throughout the frequency spectrum, this is a major improvement. The mixed mode allows us to combine the benefits of conventional phase vocoders and of wavelets in terms of an arbitrarily configurable frequency channel allocation. Moreover, time sampling can directly reflect the bandwidth allocation for each channel. The

sampling theorem exactly holds in view of the compactly supported windows in the frequency domain.

In conventional phase vocoders based on a compactly supported window in the time domain, frequency leakage of a single sinusoidal component of the signal occurs throughout the spectrum. Since the analysis atoms of the proposed representation have compact support in the frequency domain, frequency leakage is exactly confined so that interference can only occur from signal components falling in adjacent bands. Both amplitude and phase estimation of the partials benefit from this localization property.

Additional examples together with the corresponding sound files are available at <http://homepage.univie.ac.at/monika.doerfler/WarpFrames.html>

This page will be continuously updated as new examples and applications of the proposed framework become available.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

In this paper we have explored the design of perfect reconstruction phase vocoders based on nonuniform Gabor frames with arbitrary band allocation.

By means of a warping map, uniform frequency bands are mapped into nonuniform frequency bands, while keeping constant sampling rate within each band. The representation is shown to be useful in several applications adding flexibility to the well known and ubiquitous concept of phase vocoder in sound and music computing. These range from visualization of musical data to audio effects, feature extraction, coding and synthesis.

Some important aspects of the phase vocoder, in particular concerning phase estimation of the partials in each band, have been pointed out but not analytically addressed in the current contribution. These aspects are particularly useful and important in sound transformation (stretching, transposition) and their adaptation to the flexible framework introduced will be presented elsewhere.

In future work we will further consider the use of nearly perfect reconstruction nonuniform representations that are suitable for real time computation and achieve a compromise between time and frequency localization. Furthermore, a time-varying band allocation method generalizing the scheme in [12] is under investigation.

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